

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Effect of soil acidity on germination of rice

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Ninety germplasms from the 1985 Acid Lowland Soils Screening Set (IRTP) were evaluated for direct seeding in saline acid lowland soils, where high germination is a prerequisite.

Seeds were sown in triplicate, at 20 seeds/dish, in petri dishes containing 60 g of soil (silty clay) having ECe 11.3 dS/m and pH 3.2. After sowing, 40 ml of distilled water was added immediately and 10 ml water at 5d

Germination of rice germplasm in acid soil (pH 3.2, ECe 11.3 dS/m). West Bengal, India.

Varieties and lines with indicated germination percentage			
100–80%	79–10%	69–50%	49–40%
IR13423-17-1-2-1	IR13149-43-2	B2149b-Pn-26-1-1	BW295-4
IR19661-13-3-2	IR13419-113-1	IR13146-45-2	IR13168-143-1
ITA230	IR25588-7-3-1	IR13146-45-2-3	IR32
Khao Tah Haeng 17	IR31917-31-3-2	IR9764-45-2-2	IR42
Mahsuri	IR3839-1		IR4227-109-1-3-3
			IR5
			IR8192-31-2-1-2
6.7	Average height on day 15 (cm)		5.7
	6.7	6.4	

intervals. The dishes were kept at room temperature (30°C) in the laboratory for 15 d. Germination was recorded daily and the average height of seedlings per dish was measured on day 15 (see table).

Of the 90 lines, 45 did not germinate. Five entries had more than 80% germination and another 5 had 70-80%. These 10 lines seem to be promising in acid saline soils. *ℓ*

Field screening of rice cultivars in acid sulfate soils, South China

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In the more than 67,000 ha of acid sulfate soil and acid sulfate swamp in China, major factors limiting rice growth are low pH, Fe and Al toxicity,

Table 1. Chemical characteristics of the acid sulfate soil at Duanfen, South China.

Item	Depth (cm)	
	0-15	30-40
pH (H ₂ O)	3.85	3.07
pH (KCl)	3.17	2.65
Total N (%)	0.221	0.170
Organic C (%)	3.13	3.19
Available P (Olsen, ppm)	1.63	1.53
Exchangeable K (meq/100 g)	0.290	0.490
Available Zn (ppm)	7.8	8.0
Water soluble SO ₄ (meq/100 g)	0.44	4.59
Active Fe (%)	2.7	2.36
Active Mn (ppm)	20.1	25.1
Particle size (%)		
Sand (0-0.05 mm)	6.6	23.8
Silt (0.05-0.001 mm)	62.9	52.6
Clay (<0.001 mm)	30.4	23.6

Table 2. Iron toxicity tolerance scores and yields of rice with 2 fertilizer treatments on an acid sulfate soil, Duanfen, South China.^a

Variety	Iron toxicity tolerance scores ^b		
	4 WT	8 WT	Grain yield ^c (g/plot)
	<i>40 kg N + 33 kg K/ha</i>		
IR36	3.5 bc	2.0 ab	725 cd
IR50	3.5 bc	2.3 cd	815 bcd
IR58	3.4 ab	2.2 bcd	540 f
IR19058-107-1	3.6 bc	2.3 cd	125 cd
IR29725-22-3-3-3	4.0 d	2.5 d	460 f
IR13427-60-1-3-2-2	3.1 cd	2.3 bcd	750 cd
Duansan (local variety)	3.5 bc	2.1 abc	760 cd
Shanyou (hybrid variety)	3.5 bc	2.1 abc	915 ab
Guichao (local variety)	3.1 a	1.9 a	1085 a
	<i>40 kg N + 33 kg K + 17.6 kg P + 3000 kg CaO/ha</i>		
IR36	2.9 a	2.1 ab	150 cdef
IR50	3.1 a	2.3 abc	790 bcd
IR58	2.9 a	2.6 c	757 f
IR19058-107-1	2.9 a	2.3 abc	735 def
IR29725-22-3-3-3	3.4 a	2.4 bc	515 f
IR13427-60-1-3-2-2	3.5 a	2.4 bc	700 def
Duansan (local variety)	3.1 a	2.5 c	935 ab
Shanyou (hybrid variety)	3.0 a	2.4 bc	925 abc
Guichao (local variety)	2.9 a	2.0 a	1060 a

^aIn the column in the same treatment, values followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b1 = normal plant, 9 = nearly dead or dead plant, 3 = tolerant, 6 or more = susceptible. WT = weeks after transplanting. ^cAv of 3 replications.

P deficiency, and excess sulfate. Eighteen rice varieties and lines (15 from the International Rice Testing Program) were screened under 2 fertilizer

treatments, N + K and N + K + P + Ca, in an acid sulfate soil (Table 1) at Duanfen, Taishan county, Guangdong Province, Apr 1985. The amount of